

Final Design Review

Team name: ASTRA

Country: Poland

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1 CHANGELOG

- Added points 6.4, 6.5, 6.6, 8.
- Updated report numbering and points: 2, 2.1, 2.2, 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.3.1, 3.3.3, 3.4.1, 3.5, 3.6, 3.7, 4.1, 4.3, 4.4, 5.1, 5.2, 5.3, 5.5, 6.1, 6.2, 6.3, 7, 9.

2 INTRODUCTION

To create this FDR team used Autodesk Fusion 360, SOLIDWORKS Premium 2024, SOLIDWORKS Visualize 2024, Autodesk Recap Pro Photo, Canva and Microsoft Word.

2.1 Team roles and organization

Mr Daniel Pawlikowski
ASTRA team mentor.
The best physics teacher.

Wojtek Stuczyński (pilot ID: POL-RP-pg75I2afngb)
Cansat 3D designer, Cansat hardware engineer.
16-year-old surfing admirer, keen physicist and a wonderful swimmer.

Dawid Pupek (pilot ID: POL-RP-bm4uu0lqzcwz)
Cansat hardware engineer.
A 19 years old duplicate bridge and mathematics enthusiast. Also enjoys playing volleyball and guitar.

Jakub Wąsikowski - (pilot ID: POL-RP-n5rtigkq1he)
Representative, report editor, ground station engineer.
17 year old American football player in PFL and is a proud competitive sports lover. Occasionally plays card games.

Pola Nowakowska (pilot ID: POL-RP-bfeguksluax)
Social media manager, report editor, accountant, outreach specialist.
Seventeen-year-old bookworm and good music enjoyer, interested in contemporary dance.

Bartosz Dąbrowski (pilot ID: POL-RP-2g7xav5gfvec)
Software engineer, finance manager, report content manager, ground station engineer.
A 17 year old entrant in oxford debates as well as a mathematics and IT aficionado.

Antoni Wójcik (pilot ID: POL-RP-g2tp54umpyg4)
Recovery system engineer, aerodynamics specialist, ground station engineer.
A seventeen-year-old interested in DIYs, motorization and sport.

More about pilot ID in [5.4](#)

2.2 Mission objectives

To classify the probe's mission as a successful one, the cansat will have to fulfill the subsequent objectives:

Primary mission -

- Measuring temperature and pressure
- Saving the primary mission data on an onboard microSD card
- Maintaining radio communication with the ground station

Secondary mission -

- Spreading the arms and decoupling the parachute
- Maintaining controlled flight
- Surveying and taking photos of a designated area and storing them on the 32GB camera's microSD card
- Heading towards the ground station after completing the scan
- Sending its geolocation to the ground station

Other goals that the probe may achieve to surpass the expectations are:

- Returning to the ground station
- Continuous live footage from the drone's camera

Objectives that the team needs to fulfill in order to consider the whole campaign a success:

- Constructing a contour map and a 3D model of the scanned terrain using photogrammetry
- Using the 3D model for the creation ASTRA's space station™ on the scanned terrain

2.3 Inspiration

The secondary mission is inspired by the Ingenuity Mars Helicopter, made by NASA. It is the first attempt at a powered, controlled flight on another planet. The ASTRA team wants to create a technology that would allow performing a highly detailed scan of the terrain and could possibly be useful in adapting outer space for living.

3 CANSAT DESCRIPTION

3.1 Main mission overview

The main distinguishing feature of the ASTRA team's mission is the probe being a fully functioning compact drone, which can easily fit within the size limitations set by the rulebook. As a part of the aforementioned secondary mission, the flying probe will capture a series of images using a camera mounted on its bottom. Later those same images will be used to create a contour map and a 3D model of the terrain, using photogrammetry. The map and model will act as a reference and provide valuable insight for architects and engineers, which can help with designing buildings in hard-to-reach places.

The mission will be comprised of five distinctly important steps.

1. The descent:

After being released from the ESA's Cansat carrier at around 2500 meters the Cansat will deploy its parachute. After that, for around 2360 meters the probe descends using the specifically made parachute with the speed of around 5,67 meters per second. Using a reliable inflight sensor, such as the GPS, the Cansat will determine its relative altitude to the ground. When it reaches the preset altitude, the probe will transition into the second part of the main mission.

2. The splaying of the main module:

The arms with motors are connected to the parachute cords with fly lines and they are deployed along with the parachute, due to the force with which the parachute cords pull them.

3. The detachment of the parachute and starting the engines:

At the altitude of 140 m the probe arms the engines and runs the current through the heater for next 7s, which generates enough heat to melt the fly lines in a little bit less than 1s. When those 8s pass, the cansat has another second to distance itself from the falling parachute and then slowly begins to decelerate, descending to the altitude of 15 meters.

4. The scanning mission:

After lowering, the drone flies to the set starting point of the terrain scan and then begins to fly along the preset path, taking pictures every 1,3 seconds, which combined with the drone's set speed is perfect for achieving the 70%-80% overlap on photos, ideal for photogrammetric use. The drone saves the photos on an onboard microSD card and also transmits the live footage to the ground station, which is recorded by the computer as a backup. The footage is available in a range of about 4 kilometers, which should be enough for the starting campaign. It is planned to scan a terrain 250 m x 250 m on the altitude of 15m, which combined with the effective 90-degree field of view of the camera, results in needing 784 photos, equal to about 17 minutes of flying.

5. Return protocol:

After fulfilling its aforementioned scan mission, the drone starts heading towards the coordinates of the ground station and slowly descends towards the ground. When it nears the team, it will be switched into manual mode and safely landed in order not to damage any modules, especially the camera.

3.2 Mechanical/structural designⁱ

Main body

The Cansat's main body serves the purpose of housing all of the electronics and acts as the building block for all the attachments, like propeller arms and battery sockets, as well as other components shown on the model.

Hinged propeller arm

In order to properly separate the motors from the main body and achieve the required wingspan to provide adequate stabilization for the Cansat when it engages the engines in the open position. The hinged arms are used to house and space out the engines mounted at the end of each arm. On one of them, a BME280 module is mounted to address potential issues related to heating modules inside the probe (can be observed on the picture).

Engines

The flight during the main mission is supported by four individually powered CADDXFPV 1303 6000KV motors, which are attached to the arms each via three standard M2 bolts.

Propellers

The four engines, equipped with HQProp T3020-2 propellers, are able to generate a sufficient 600 grams of upward thrust, which will enable the probe to be steered and maneuverer freely.

Arm splaying system

The spreading of the arms will be possible, due to fly lines connected to the parachute cords wrapped around the heater, which is used there as a transmission. After the detachment of the parachute, the air drag pushing onto propellers and armed engines hold the arms in place.

Battery sockets

In order to support the power demands of a flight mission, the main body will store four batteries inside the specially designed sockets to ensure efficient energy transfer and a snug fit.

The parachute detachment system

The heater mounted on the bottom of the main chassis melts four fluorocarbon fly lines, attached to the parachute cords, simultaneously. The heater has a power of 40W, which means that if current runs through it for 7 seconds, it heats up to 210-220 degrees Celcius. The melting point of fluorocarbon fly lines is 170 degrees Celcius. As shown by the tests in [6.4](#), the lines melt on average in 7,43 seconds from the start of heating, and the heater does not heat up enough to melt the plastic casing. The plastic casing is now also painted with heat-resistant paint, which significantly delays the heating of plastic elements touching the heater.

3.3 Electrical Design

Primary mission & secondary missionⁱⁱ

3.3.1 Hardware

Microcontrollers

Arduino Nano Everyⁱⁱⁱ – primary mission controlling unit and secondary mission supporting unit. It is responsible for formatting GPS and BME modules data, saving it on onboard microSD card, and sending it through LoRa module. Turns on and off the heater in the parachute detachment system. Also, it sends the manipulated signal, identical to the signal sent by RC drone controller, to the motors controlling unit, in order for it to proceed to engine arming instructions and auto-pilot functions.

iFlight BLITZ Whoop F7 55A AIO, further FC board^{iv} – main secondary mission controlling unit. Is responsible for engines thrust management, routing the Cansat and distributing power between all the secondary mission modules and Arduino Nano Every.

Modules – primary mission

Ra-02 LoRa module^v – radio communication module. Sends GPS and BME modules data to ground station, using 433MHz radio waves.

BME280 5V^{vi} – temperature and pressure measuring module. It is chosen, due to its small size and compatibility with Arduino’s 5V logic. Is mounted on one of the arms to resolve potential heat issues with other components.

MicroSD Card Module^{vii} – responsible for saving primary mission data on microSD card.

Modules – secondary mission

iFlight Anti Spark Filter^{viii} - reduces sparking, when connecting a battery to an electrical circuit, protecting components from damage and reducing wear on contacts. Also helps reduce voltage spikes, that can occur during connection.

iFlight Blitz M10 V2 20x21 GPS with QMC5883 Compass^{ix} – GPS module with built-in compass. Connected to Arduino Nano Every and FC board by UART. Connecting the UART devices like in the schematic above, allows both devices to listen to GPS module, despite UART being designed to connect only two devices.

Walksnail AVATAR HD kit V2 32G^x – Camera module with built-in 32GB storage for videos and pictures from flight and AVATAR V2 VTX. The VTX (video transmitter) operates in the 5.725-5.850 GHz frequencies, has 4 kilometers of range, and enables probe to send real-time video signals from the camera to a ground receiver. The stock 160-degree camera lens is replaced with a 90-degree one, to negate the effects that the “fisheye” lens would have on the final model.

TBS Tracer Nano RX^{xi} - long-range receiver, enabling people in the ground support team to manually control the Cansat, using a controller. Useful in emergency situations and landing performance.

CADDXFPV 1303 6000KV motors^{xii}- engines, each capable of generating 150g of thrust with the current drone setup (appropriate propellers and battery discharge current), providing a large power reserve for control and balancing, even in fairly challenging conditions. Additionally, they are significantly more efficient compared to 11500KV motors, which draw much more current and were unsuitable for the mission performed by the drone.

Heater - part of the parachute detachment system. It heats up to the temperature of 210-220 degrees Celsius, which is more than enough to melt the fly lines holding the parachute, and not damage any of the components inside. It is controlled by the Arduino Nano Every board, which uses N-MOSFET IRLZ34N transistor to turn on and off the flow of current between the batteries and a heater. The circuit also uses a 10kOhm pull-down resistor to prevent any possibility of unplanned activation of the heating element.

Batteries

4x 18650 Li-Ion Samsung INR18650 3500mAh – have the capacity of 3500mAh, voltage of 3,6V and maximal discharge current of 8A.

These batteries are connected in series, reaching the total capacity 3500mAh, nominal voltage of 14,4V and maximal discharge current of 8A.

3.3.2 PCB design

In order to reduce the number of wires and ensure the reliability of the connection of the primary mission modules (except BME280 due to temperature issues) with the Arduino board, a PCB board has been designed, made and electrical components were soldered onto it. The idea is considered to be a great achievement and is working perfectly fine.

3.3.3 Flight time calculations

Battery Configuration:

4x 18650 Li-Ion Samsung INR18650 3500mAh

Total energy in 4S configuration:

Total capacity: 3,5 Ah

Total energy: $14,4 V \times 3,5 Ah = 50,4 Wh$

Consumption:

Motors: $4 \times 14,4 \text{ V} \times 1,4 \text{ A} = 80,64 \text{ W}$

Walksnail HD Kit: $14,4 \text{ V} \times 0,3 \text{ A}$ (maximum) = $4,32 \text{ W}$

FC board: $14,4 \text{ V} \times 0,41 \text{ A} = 5,9 \text{ W}$

Primary mission and Arduino Nano Every: $1,57 \text{ W}$

Total power: $92,43 \text{ W}$

Post-Flight Operation:

Pre-flight and post-flight power for 7 hours: $1,57 \text{ W} \times 7 = 10,99 \text{ Wh}$ (safe backup)

Energy available for flight: $50,4 \text{ Wh} - 10,99 \text{ Wh} = 39,41 \text{ Wh}$

Flight Time:

$39,41 \text{ Wh} / 92,43 \text{ W} \approx 0,427 \text{ h} = 25,62 \text{ minutes}$

The flight time of 25,62 minutes should be entirely sufficient to fulfill the scan, as the time needed to reach the planned area and perform the scan mission is estimated to be around 17 minutes. It may also last to execute the return protocol, as this consequent task is set to take no more than 5 minutes.

3.4 Recovery system

3.4.1 Parachute^{xiii}

The most crucial part of the recovery system is the parachute. It ensures that the Cansat reaches the preassigned altitude at a safe speed. The parachute will be comprised of eight identical panels, which are made out of Nylon Ripstop D20. At an altitude of 100m-90m above the ground, the parachute is detached.

The parachute is attached to the body with the use of nylon and polyester thread with thicker ends and thin fluorocarbon fly lines.

3.4.2 Live footage and GPS data

Receiving the live footage from the camera and GPS data will allow the ground team to accurately determine the Cansat's location.

3.4.3 Return protocol

At the end of its mission, the probe will begin heading to the location of the ground station. Upon getting within 100 meters of the ground crew, the Cansat will be switched into manual mode and get flown to a safe location by one of the crew members qualified to do so (all members of ASTRA already have the required in Poland A1/A3 certificates to pilot drones up to 25 kg).

3.5 Ground support equipment

The ground station will use the tuned YAGI antenna to establish and maintain connection with the Cansat and receive data packs, containing the telemetric data and probe's location to aid the recovery team with the Cansat's retrieval. The data packs will be sent every half a second to give the ground crew information whether the connection to the Cansat is maintained.

Antenna mount

To maintain adequate and efficient connection with the Cansat and maximize the antenna's receiving ability, the antenna will be mounted on a tripod equipped with a mechanical rig at the top. Giving the ground crew the ability to mechanically aim the antenna using a controller connected to the servos installed inside the rig. It is specially designed by the team. The rig is able to swiftly rotate along two axes giving it a full 360-degree range of motion in the horizon and about a 270-degree range of motion vertically.

To enable the movement of the robotic rig, the team embedded RDS3115mg servo motors in the specially designed slots. The motors are able to easily and safely maneuver the antenna and point it in the direction of the Cansat.

In order to precisely move and aim the receiver, without disturbing the receiving of data, the ground support team uses the ground station control console, in particular the 4 buttons.

The ground station setup is powered through 5V 3A DC power supply unit and a laptop.

VRX receiver^{xiv}

To receive the real-time video from the Cansat's camera, the ground station will be using the Walksnail AVATAR VRX, fully compatible with the onboard VTX. The received video will be additionally saved on the ground station's PC.

Ground station control console

Digital display^{xv}

The ground unit will be equipped with an internally routed housing for the Adafruit 1480 digital display, which displays the team logo and basic information about the received data.

Power and analog ports

In order to power and maintain connection with the external components, such as the Yagi antenna, servos and the laptop team designed three outputs for USB cable, female SMA connector and cables for powering the servo motors and the control console. Even if powered only through the laptop, the LoRa receiver and the screen still work.

Custom 3D printed inserts

Button plate

A solid plate insert fitted with four specially designed button housings, each of which is made with cable holes for the tactile THT switches.

Screen housing

Two pieces of external protection, which allow the screen to fit snugly in its casing.

Miniature spinning antenna

Looks cool and indicates that everything is powered and works properly.

Cable management port

A side insert was created using two different filaments. For the outer shell team used ZORTRAX's ULTRA-T, due to its superior durability when compared to other filaments. However, for the inner circular inserts, the 3D team elected to use ZORTRAX's Z-FLEX because of its pliability, which will allow the cables to move smoothly and without the risk of damage.

Custom built switches

Since there are no commercially available switches that fit the needs of this situations the 3D modelling team created their own. They were later hand primed and painted

TBS Mambo remote flight controller^{xvi}

Is used for taking control of the drone in emergency situations or for the landing part. Combined with onboard receiver, has a range of 25 kilometers.

More photos of ground station can be found [here](#).

3.6 Software Design

The components of the primary mission are controlled by an Arduino Nano Every board using a custom team-developed code.

The probe equipped with the iFlight BLITZ Whoop F7 55A AIO board utilizes the ArduPilot^{xvii} software for motor control, due to the complexity of thrust regulation and the high importance of reliability in this aspect of the mission.

The ground station operates the Arduino Portenta H7 microcontroller, fully programmed by the team. The way this functions is that the Arduino Portenta H7 receives the telemetric data from the probe, and this data is transmitted to the main computer via serial port and automatically saved. The team also receives the geolocation of the cansat, which is shown on the main computer on the map, and based on this map, the person can adjust the antenna, using buttons, to track the cansat.

All the information received and sent by the main computer will be displayed on its screen in real-time to enable potential debugging. In any case of system malfunction due to unforeseen circumstances, it will be possible to manually control the antenna on the stand, by disabling the servos' torque, allowing the physical rotation.

All of the code written by the team, is available for inspection [here](#).

3.7 Post-processing

Primary mission data will be analyzed and turned into a graph displaying the dependence between temperature and altitude.

Pictures taken by camera and GPS data from the secondary mission will be used in Recap Pro^{xviii}, a software by Autodesk specialized in photogrammetry, to create a contour map and a detailed 3D model of the scanned terrain (containing the editable cloud of points, saved as the mesh model, allowing for manual correction of the model issues). The next step will be using the created 3D model in Autodesk Revit, Civil 3D, or Fusion 360 to plan there the ASTRA's space station™.

As a way to utilize the data, ASTRA's 3D modelling team will create a model of a space station sitting on top of the scouted terrain, which will be made to showcase different uses of such maps and problems that this technology solves. The map with integrated model will be shown during the final presentation.

All of this software is free to use for students, thanks to the Autodesk educational license. A couple of software programs have been compared (Recap Pro, 3DEXPERIENCE GeoModeler, Agisoft Metashape), and Recap Pro turned out to generate the best models from the drone's photos.

4 PROJECT PLANNING

4.1 Time schedule

	Hardware	Software	Outreach	Budget & Sponsors	Reports & Other
September	Prototype the model of CanSat	Develop primary mission software	Set out Social Media profiles	Plan budget, creating a list of sponsors	Online industry training (26-27)
October	Print parts of the CanSat and finish the antenna mount	Begin development of the secondary mission software		Start to secure sponsors and funds	Hand in of Preliminary Design Review (20)
November	Test fit all components in the CanSat	Finish the ground station software			Online workshops
December		Finish the development of the secondary mission software		Finish securing all the needed funds from sponsors	
January			Conduct workshops in primary schools,		Hand in of Critical Design Review (18)
February	FIRST FLIGHTS / SECONDARY MISSION TESTS	Creating first contour map and 3D model of the terrain	Appearance in the local newspaper and on TV, visit the local radio, Set up a website		
March	Further tests on different altitudes to find the most efficient one, resolving potential issues	Detailing of the 3D model creation process			Hand in of Final Design Review (24)

Legend:

Green - done

Yellow – under development

Red – not done yet

4.2. Tasks division

<p>Wojciech Stuczyński</p>	<p>Create the 3D model of the Cansat, design and create the parachute decoupling system, design and create the arms splaying system, solder the Cansat parts, design and create the wiring in the Cansat, print the 3D printable parts</p>
<p>Dawid Pupek</p>	<p>Design the parachute decoupling system with Wojtek, create the arms splaying system, design and create the arms splaying system with Wojtek, solder the Cansat parts, design the Cansat's main body</p>
<p>Jakub Wąsikowski</p>	<p>Editing the reports, creation of the ground station mechanical design and putting the antenna mount and the antenna together, writing of the sponsoring requests and presenting the ASTRA's Cansat project</p>
<p>Pola Nowakowska</p>	<p>Editing the reports, creation of the posts for ASTRA's Instagram and TikTok, redacting the blog, account the invoices, coordination of the team's actions and keeping the calendar</p>
<p>Bartosz Dąbrowski</p>	<p>Format and supervise the contents of the reports, develop the ground station software, create a wiring schematic, develop the primary mission software, manage the secondary mission software, create a website, create, update and direct the budget, prepare the workshops' base</p>
<p>Antoni Wójcik</p>	<p>Wire the ground station, supervising the electrical circuits and safety of the Cansat and ground station, design, sew and create the parachute, prepare the segment of the workshops</p>

4.3 Resource estimation

Parts – Cansat	Price in PLN	Price in EUR
Arduino Nano Every	65 PLN	15,11 EUR
iFlight BLITZ Whoop F7 AIO	494 PLN	114,84 EUR
iFlight Anti Spark Filter	70 PLN	16,27 EUR
iFlight Blitz mini M10 V2 GPS	189 PLN	43,94 EUR
Walksnail AVATAR HD kit V2 32G	701 PLN	162,96 EUR
TBS Tracer Nano RX	131 PLN	31,48 EUR
4x CADDX 1303 6000KV	236 PLN	54 EUR
Ra-02 LoRa module	31 PLN	7,21 EUR
MicroSD Card module	19,04 PLN	4,43 EUR
BME280 5V	15 PLN	3,49 EUR
4x 18650 batteries	144 PLN	34,61 EUR
Parachute and lines	30,5 PLN	7,33 EUR
PCB	2,15 PLN	0,5 EUR
Propellers	28 PLN	6,73 EUR
Cables	9 PLN	2,16 EUR
Screws and bolts	5 PLN	1,16 EUR
Heater	36 PLN	8,65 EUR
32 GB microSD card	26 PLN	6,04 EUR
Transistors and resistors	3,4 PLN	0,81 EUR
Sum	2235,09 PLN	521,72 EUR

4.4 Mass budget

Parts - Cansat	Weight
4x engines + 8x propellers	26,4 grams
TBS Tracer Nano RX	1 gram
Primary mission PCB with components	13 grams
BME280 5V	1,5 grams
Walksnail AVATAR HD kit V2 32G	25,5 grams
iFlight BLITZ Whoop F7 AIO	10 grams
iFlight Anti Spark Filter	4,5 grams
Batteries	184 grams
GPS module	8 grams
Parachute with cords and lines	13,5 grams

Heater	3 grams
Plastic elements	27,8 grams
Antennas	8,5 grams
Other – cables, bolts, transistor etc.	21,9 grams
Sum	348,6 grams

5 OUTREACH PROGRAMME

5.1 SOCIAL MEDIA AND WEBSITE

As for today, ASTRA has significantly developed their [Instagram profile](#), gaining a new audience (643 followers in total) by updating the progress they make on building the probe as well as sharing entertaining elements revolving around the main theme of the project. Over half of the team’s viewers are non-followers, with average number of 3056 views under post and over 40000 in total. Activity under Instagram posts are presented here:

(Pink – followers, purple non-followers)

Moreover, the team has set up [TikTok profile](#), to broaden their audience across different platforms by posting similar content.

ASTRA has updated their [website](#), where information about the progress of team's work can be found.

5.2 EDUCATION

ASTRA already organized educational meetings in SP 2, SP 7, SP 29 in Olsztyn, in order to share knowledge about the CanSat competition, team's experiences regarding their project as well as the goals of their mission. Having said that, ASTRA's main message mission was to show that learning strict subjects can be much more entertaining than they seem. Photos from these workshops can be [found here](#). Altogether, the team has conducted workshops for over 300 students.

5.3 PUBLIC SPACES

In the second part of the competition, ASTRA had contacted local media, newspapers, radio and television to popularize our project on the premises of Warmińsko-Mazurskie voivodeship, or even all around the country. These actions allowed the team to gain a larger audience.

In February, ASTRA was made a guest during a broadcast in Radio Olsztyn – Obserwatorium Nowych Technologii (Observatory of New Technologies), thanks to the kindness of Mr. Marek Lewiński. Full interview and article can be found [here](#). Moreover, the team was mentioned in articles, written by the local newspaper - [Twój Kurier Olsztyński](#). and [Gazeta Olsztyńska](#). Due to unforeseen scheduling difficulties the team was not able to arrange a meeting with the local TV in time for the FDR report.

Thankfully all the calls have been made and the programme should air between March 30th and April 2nd.

5.4 EXTERNAL SUPPORT

Thanks to Uniwersytet Warmińsko - Mazurski in Olsztyn, ASTRA members obtained [drone pilot certificates](#) on category A1/A3 (operator numbers present in 1.1), necessary to steer a drone up to 25 kg at an altitude of 120 m above sea level. Moreover, Wydział Nauk Technicznych has officially become the team's substantive patron. From now on, the team is entitled to use the university's machines and equipment, but also enables ASTRA to inquire opinions of professionals, regarding our project.

ASTRA has successfully fulfilled the budget goals, thanks to team's sponsors, who are:

The sponsors above have provided the team with funds (14 531,52 PLN in total), discounts and time-limited licenses for crucial software.

5.5 OTHER

ASTRA team has already designed hoodies with their logo. The hoodies are planned to be made before the finals as they do not serve an important role in Cansat's functionality.

The hoodies have already been ordered by the team's sponsor and are soon to be received by the members of ASTRA.

6 TEST CAMPAIGN

6.1 Primary mission tests

Software tests

The ASTRA team had the opportunity to test the operation of LoRa during a flight organised by Politechnika Warszawska. The team's Cansat was supposed to be lifted by a rubber balloon to an altitude of approximately 2.5 kilometers and was actually dropped 100 meters below that height. The Cansats were placed in a secure compartment and thanks to the GPS system, the team was able to track the balloon's position. The experiment was fully successful, and the probe was lifted to the expected altitude. Communication with the Cansat was maintained for a long time – up until it flew into a built – up area, around 500 m above sea level, allowing the team to successfully receive the required information about temperature, pressure, and altitude. Although the test went very well, the team was unable to recover the probe. Despite adverse weather conditions, the falling Cansat transmitted data using the LoRa module almost until the very end of the flight. Photo documentation from the project can be found [here](#) and on ASTRA's Instagram profile.

PCB board, BME280 and LoRa tests

The test has been carried over the distances of 30 meters, around 210 meters, and 860 meters. The places and distances are visible below.

The RSSI of the received packets, with proper telemetric data, on the given distances turned out as follows: -68, -83, and -108, which is considered exceptionally great by the team and fully satisfies them. Also, the telemetric data has been successfully saved onto the onboard microSD card. [Photos from the test.](#)

6.2 Secondary mission tests

The secondary mission components have been successfully connected together and tested out outdoors.

Outcome: Each component operates as intended, and the Cansat's ability to sustain flight has been successfully tested. The probe performed a stable and manageable flight. Since the drone doesn't have advanced manual flight support systems, which is why flying it manually has proven more challenging than expected. However, autonomous flight has no such limitations. [Video from the test.](#)

6.3 Parachute tests

Parachute test was carried out from an altitude of 11 meters. The altitude, where CanSat reached the actual descending velocity, is considered to be 8,5 meters, therefore the falling time reaches 1,5 seconds. This defines CanSat's descending velocity to be approximately 5,67 m/s.

Outcome: the parachute maintains a straight flight path, does not encounter turbulence, and descends at an appropriate speed. [Video from the test.](#)

6.4 Heater tests (detachment system)

The tests were conducted in a home environment in a room with a temperature of 18 degrees Celsius. Three independent tests have shown that the heater melts all four wires simultaneously and takes an average of slightly below 7,5 seconds from the moment the current starts flowing through it. Additionally, a test was conducted to confirm that, as expected, when the heater is connected to power for the designated 6,5 seconds, it heats up sufficiently to melt a wire in slightly less than a second after the heating ends, while leaving the plastic components holding it intact. [Testing videos.](#)

6.5 Arms splaying tests

The task of the arm deployment system is to extend them from the space where they are positioned so that the arming of the engines is possible. Tests have proven that our system is capable of extending the arms each time by more than a 45-degree angle, which easily allows for air resistance, and then the arming of the engines to set them in the target position (90 degrees). It can also be observed on the secondary mission tests [Video from the test.](#)

6.6 Camera tests and 3D models

During these tests, the drone conducted an autonomous flight over a 100m x 100m area at altitudes of 10 meters, 15 meters, and 30 meters. The scan that achieved the best quality-to-coverage ratio per image was the one taken at 15 meters. Nevertheless, all scans exceeded the team's expectations in terms of quality. The winning scan took 2.5 minutes and captured 93 images suitable for further processing, achieving 86% horizontal coverage and 74% vertical coverage. The flight was conducted over a ploughed field, and our scan perfectly captured the terrain's curvature.

Below are images of the flight path and the 3D model itself.

There is also 3D model file and photos from the test [here](#).

7 CANSAT CHARACTERISTICS

Characteristics	Figure
Height of the CanSat	114 millimeters
Diameter of the CanSat	66 millimeters
Mass of the CanSat	348,6 grams
Estimated descent rate	5,67 m/s
Radio transmitter model and frequency	SX1278 from Ra-02, 433 MHz
Estimated time on battery	7h (Cansat mode) / 25,6 minutes - drone
Cost of the CanSat	521,72 EUR

8 SAFETY MEASURES

Arming conditions

The software's built-in requirements that must be met for the drone's propellers to be activated are as follows:

- The drone must be facing upwards - if the gyroscope detects that the drone is angled at more than 35 degrees in any way, the engines don't arm
- All four batteries must be connected
- All of the basic components needed to perform the flight must be functional, which are GPS, accelerometer, gyroscope, magnetometer, camera and engines.
- The TBS mambo flight controller from the ground station must be connected

Without these, the drone will refuse to start the engines every time.

The heating element

The heater doesn't turn on if the engines refuse to arm.

If engines arm properly, the heater works for 7s, then it is turned off by the Arduino Nano Every board and the pin responsible for controlling the transistor is shut down by the code line "pinMode(heater_pin, INPUT_PULLDOWN)", which disables pin from being on HIGH state ever again, until the board is reset.

The plastic casing, which is used to mount the heater, is additionally painted with heat-resistant paint, which significantly reduces the heat given to the plastic parts.

Although the melting time of the fly lines is extremely consistent, there is a time buffer of 0,7 second to ensure that the parachute becomes detached.

Safety key

The top of the battery casing is designed with a push-and-twist system, which means that it is pushed in place and then twisted to be secured. The only way to detach the top part is to use the specially designed key. There are three prepared for the jury on the starting campaign, however team is ready to prepare more copies if needed. This is the main way to turn the probe off.

Another way is to use the mambo controller to disarm engines and turn the drone off.

9 REFERENCES

Links to datasheets and websites used for gathering data for descriptions, calculations, and the creation of the models and schematics, present in this report.

- ⁱ [Model of the Cansat in STEP file and more photos of the CanSat](#)
- ⁱⁱ [Schematics in PDF files for better visibility](#)
- ⁱⁱⁱ [Arduino Nano Every datasheet](#)
- ^{iv} [iFlight Blitz Whoop F7 55A AIO wiring diagram](#)
- ^v [Ra-02 LoRa module datasheet](#)
- ^{vi} [BME280 technical overview site](#)
- ^{vii} [MicroSD card module producer's product site](#)
- ^{viii} [Anti-spark filer producer's product site](#)
- ^{ix} [GPS module producer's product site](#)
- ^x [Camera module producer's product site](#)
- ^{xi} [TBS Tracer RX producer's site](#)
- ^{xii} [CADDX motor producer's site](#)
- ^{xiii} [Websites used for calculating the parachute surface and creating the panels](#)
- ^{xiv} [Walksnail AVATAR VRX producer's product site](#)
- ^{xv} [Adafruit 1480](#)
- ^{xvi} [TBS Mambo producer's website](#)
- ^{xvii} [ArduPilot developer's site](#)
- ^{xviii} [Recap Pro's description site](#)